

PHILOSOPHICAL INTERPRETATION OF ISSUES OF SPIRITUALITY AND ENLIGHTENMENT IN CENTRAL ASIAN PHILOSOPHICAL THOUGHT

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Abstract: Central Asia has long been one of the ancient centers of scientific knowledge and culture. Thinkers of this country have enriched world science, culture, spirituality and philosophical thought with their discoveries, advanced socio-philosophical, moral views. Those who have effectively influenced his progress.

Monuments indicating the level of development of scientific knowledge in Central Asia have reached little until our time. But the above-mentioned sources indicate that in Central Asia from time immemorial he had achieved some success in the field of astronomy, mathematics, geometry, Geodesy, physics, medicine and other natural-scientific knowledge.

Keywords: spirituality, perfect man, society, humanity, education, patriotism

The 9th and 12th centuries were a new stage, which took a huge place in the development of cultural and scientific knowledge of the peoples of Central Asia. This period is referred to in history as the first renaissance in Central Asia. During this period, in the development of scientific and religious knowledge, Central Asia became one of the central foci of World Culture. The emergence of feudal states, centered around the end of the Arab conquest, led to the development of trade and cultural ties, the growth of scientific knowledge. In particular, the location of Central Asia over the route of East and west trade and cultural relations (which now made history under the name of the "Great Silk Road") greatly influenced the development of scientific knowledge and culture in the region. In the same period, thinkers grew up who left an indelible mark on the development of World Science and culture.

In the process of farming, handicrafts and the progress of trade, there was a need to develop natural empirical knowledge. In accordance with this, the advanced thinkers of Central Asia studied mathematics, astronomy, geography, Medicine in depth, advanced new scientific ideas about scientific knowledge.

It is worth noting that the Arab Caliphate also needed natural - scientific knowledge in addition to religious knowledge. Among the Arabs themselves, the

people of this workable science were very few and weak. That is why they tried to make it possible for those who were engaged in science in the places they conquered. Cities such as Bukhara, Urganch, Marv, Balkh, Baghdad, Shom became the scientific center of the early medieval East. And Arabic became the language of science, creativity. Central Asian thinkers studied Arabic perfectly and finished their works in this language. Works in Roman, Greek, Hindi, Persian were translated into Arabic.

Another of the scientific centers that operated in Central Asia was the Samarkand (Ulughbek) Academy, which operated under the Timurid ruler Mirzo Ulughbek (1394-1449y). The Madrasa of Ulughbek in Samarkand was not only a higher religious institution, but also an Academy of the time when it was taken along with the Observatory (1424-1428y) built under Ulughbek's leadership. The famous scientist of that time, mathematician and astronomer Kazizoda Rumi, Ghiyosiddin Jamshid al-Koshiy, Nizamiddin al-Birjandiy, Ulugbek's talented disciple Ali Qushchi and others conducted scientific activities at this academy.

If the 9th-12th centuries are recognized as the first Renaissance – Renaissance of Central Asia, then the 14th-16th centuries as The Last Renaissance took place from the history of the development of scientific knowledge..

At the same time we found it necessary to provide information on the concept of Renaissance – Renaissance, the essence of the content of the eastern and Western Renaissance, the common, similar sides and differences between them. After all, this is important in understanding the eastern Renaissance, its place in Universal Civilization.

In science, the concepts of the eastern and Western renaissance are used. Together with common, similar sides, they also stand out in terms of a certain difference, their own characteristics. First of all, they differ from the point of view of the period. While the early Eastern Renaissance includes the 9th-12th centuries and The Last Renaissance includes the 14th-15th centuries, the Western renaissance is differentiated by the inclusion of the 14th-16th centuries. For the Western Renaissance, the struggle against feudalism, against religion is characteristic, while in the East we will not see the issue put as sharply as in the West.

The founder of early medieval science in Central Asia is Muhammad ibn Musa Khwarazmi (783-850y). The great fame to the scientist was originally brought by his treatise "account al-hind" ("account of the Indian"). This booklet

tells about the decimal position system and its importance for the first time in the history of World Science. Khorezmi's decimal position system has provided humanity with endless favorable opportunities. If it were not for this counting system, the commandment that scientific thought would find evolution to this extent would have been ignored. Khorezmi discovered a counting system that records infinite quantities using an Indian number of nine characters and represents it with ease. In order for the Indian Nine-character numeral system to become a perfect numeral system, "0" had to be discovered and replaced. The discovery of "0"(zero)by Khwarezmi is one of the incomparable achievements of human scientific thought. Now no one can deny the fact that on the basis of the tremendous achievements of modern world science and technology, the great Allama Khwarazmian genius lay down.. Khwarazmi's "account al-hind" developed the six most important arithmetic operations – addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, leveling, and square rooting. Their style and laws have been discovered.

Abu Nasr Farabi (873-950) was a prominent thinker of the medieval Muslim East, the largest follower and propagandist of ancient Greek philosophy. As a connoisseur of ancient Greek science and philosophy, he translated into Arabic the works of Aristotle "metaphysics", "Physics", "Meteorology", "categories", "analytics", "rhetoric" and others, as well as the works of Euclid, Ptolemy, Hippocrates, Galenes, and wrote commentaries on them. With this, Farabi played a large role in introducing the peoples of the East, and later the peoples of Europe, to Greek science, philosophy and culture. In particular, he gained a reputation for interpreting Aristotelian philosophy, earning high names such as "Al mulamti as-soniy"-i.e. "the second teacher" and "Aristotle of the East".

The noble works, which served for the sake of human perfection, consider beautiful human qualities as good. Bad habits such as laziness, idleness, ignorance, unconsciousness, lack of professional skills, which hinder the perfection of a person, warn people from him, calling them evil.

The supreme goal of Farabi's life is to achieve happiness, which people see as achieved through the study of the universe, the acquisition of professions and Sciences-enlightenment.

Thus, the worldview of Farabi, his holistic teaching about society and morality, became important in the development of socio-philosophical, political and spiritual, moral thought in the early Middle Ages and later periods.

One of the great geniuses of the Middle Ages, the qomusi scholar Abu Rayhon Beruniy (973-1048y.) is. He mastered all subjects of his time, first of all falakiyot (Astronomy), Physics, Mathematics (Mathematics), theology, cultural studies. With Ibn Sina, the great scientist of the berunian time, he corresponded in a question-and-answer manner with the philosophy of Nature, Physics in other disciplines, of which 18 reached. In this correspondence, two famous scientists have engaged in scientific debate on issues such as space, the scattering of heat, the expansion of bodies from heat, the reflection and refraction of light. In 1017, Khwarazm operated at the Ma'mun Academy in cooperation with the famous people of science of the time.

The scientific legacy left by berunius consists of 152 books and brochures. Of these, 70 are devoted to falakiyot, 20 to mathematics, 12 to geography and geodesy, 3 to cultural studies, 15 to history and science, 4 to philosophy, 18 to literature, 4 to mapping, 3 to climatology, physics, medicine and other sciences. These include "relics from ancient peoples", "India", "Geodesy", "Minerology", "The law of the Goddess", "Elementary concepts from the art of astrology", "Saydana" and other works. Although Berunius did not write a work on philosophical-moral issues, many of his works made remarks on the issue.

According to Berunius, there are different cases in the world for people. It is praise-good and condemnation – evil. The praiseworthy are good cases, showing that purity and cleanliness make up their backbone.

Berunius was the most prominent patron of science of his time. He saw the prosperity of the country in the prosperity of science, enlightenment. Science believed that enlightenment could serve sahatly. He writes, "My whole mind is lost, my heart is focused on promoting knowledge, because I have enjoyed the pleasure of gaining knowledge. I consider this a great happiness for myself".

The conclusion is that the scientific genius of our compatriot Beruni is an important contribution to the development of universal scientific knowledge. It is also not for nothing that it is referred to in Europe as al-Baron. In our country, the study of the scientific heritage of Beruniy is widely established. For achievements in the field of Science and technology, the State Prize named after Beruniy was established.

Abu Ali ibn Sina (980-1037) was a great Hakim, qomusian alloma, and famous thinker. He was engaged in medicine, philosophy, logic, psychology, physiology, ethics, natural science, pedagogy, musicology and other fields of science.

In his youth, Ibn Sina went to study the sciences with great work, research, enthusiasm. He said of it, " even during my sleep, I could see the issues right behind me. In this case, many issues would be obvious to me in a dream... In this way I was able to master all the sciences firmly. I took possession of the knowledge that a person possesses at the level of opportunity. Aristotle's "metaphysics "was"re-read forty-one times". He even became an ode to me. But despite this, I could not understand him and his goals," writes in his biography. Ibn Sina solves this problem by reading Forobius ' commentary on Aristotle's "metaphysics". His efforts in the possession of the sciences are a sign for us.

Various sources record that he wrote more than 450 works. But up to us about 250 have arrived. Of these, 80 are devoted to philosophy, 50 to medicine, more than 40 to nature and the humanities, 3 to music and other areas of science.

Ibn Sina's scientific heritage can be conditionally divided into 4 parts- philosophical, natural, literary and medical. The scientist made a blessed creation in each of these, leaving us a rich scientific and literary legacy for generations. In his socio-political views, Alloma describes man as a socially great creature. The mutually beneficial cooperation of people claims that they are the only backbone of their lives. And in his philosophical-moral works, he calls on rulers to fight against lawlessness, listen to the demands of the ring, to act in Justice. Justice is shown to be the best decoration of the human act.

The poet Ahmad Yugnaki, who created a work on a moral-didactic topic and gained fame during the period we were studying, was born. He lived and worked in the late 12th and first half of the 13th century.. He believes that a person rises to the level of glory only after becoming a scientist and leaves a good name. An ignorant person pretends to be dead, even if he is healthy. He argues that knowledge is an inexhaustible property for a person. Poet, morality-the main thing in etiquette is language. Language encourages that it is the cause of happiness and unhappiness. At the same time, the scientist condemns greed and bad luck, saying that honesty and truthfulness, generosity are qualities for a person, it is necessary to strive for it. Camaraderie and humility show that man is glorified.

The conclusion is that during the 9th-12th centuries, science, science, enlightenment, spirituality, developed at a high level in Central Asia.

Thus, the spiritual and educational views of the peoples of Central Asia are considered an integral part of the rich spiritual heritage of our people. In the

spiritual and educational views of the peoples of Central Asia, the problems of Man and his qualities, education, morality occupied a central place. It should be noted separately that the problem of a perfect person has its own solution in its own way..

CONCLUSION

Perfection is the main criterion for spirituality. Striving to possess this quality is a perfect goal for every person. A perfect person, on the other hand, is able to put the interests of the homeland, the nation and the people above his own. The more people with this quality make up the majority in the country, the higher it develops, stability is ensured.

The development of spirituality and enlightenment and the formation of perfection through them remain an important factor in strengthening our independence.

The great generation-an incredibly rich and colorful spiritual and educational heritage created by our ancestors-still serves all peoples today as the flower crown of world civilization. This in turn will undoubtedly arouse pride in every Uzbek child and will continue to strengthen the desire to master them deeply..

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